

Comparative Analysis of Free Radical Scavenging in *Moringa oleifera*, *Sauropus androgynus* and Their Dynamic Synergy

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ABSTRACT

Background: Antioxidants play an important role in guarding the cells from oxidative damage due to free radicals. *Moringa oleifera* and *Sauropus androgynus* are known leafy plants which have satisfying nutritive value and medicinal properties. There is a lack of data on antioxidant activity of combination extract. **Objective:** This study aims to assess the antioxidant potential of *Moringa oleifera*, *Sauropus androgynus* methanolic leaf extracts, and the combination extract of the two plant leaves. **Materials and Methods:** 100g of each plant sample combination was extracted with 99% methanol. Preliminary qualitative phytochemical screening tests were performed for each extract. DPPH and ABTS assay were performed for three plant extracts and two standard solutions (ascorbic acid and BHT) at five concentrations. Percentage of inhibition and IC50 value were calculated. **Results and Discussion:** Kruskal-Wallis H test was performed for the non-normally distributed data. Significant difference in the percentage of free radical inhibition value between the five antioxidants was observed ($P < 0.05$). Ascorbic acid showed the highest performance among the five antioxidants (mean rank=14.00) in both assays. Among the three plant samples, *Moringa oleifera* shown the highest free radical scavenging activity (mean rank=8.00). The combination extract shown superior performance at high extract concentration (1000 μ g/mL). The rich vitamin and lipid contents possessed by *Sauropus androgynus* leaves promised its nutritive value for dietary and herbal supplement purposes. **Conclusion:** The addition of *Sauropus androgynus* leaf extract in *Moringa oleifera* leaf herbal formulation is promising and considerable with its own nutritive value.

Keywords: ABTS, antioxidant activity, combination extract, DPPH, free radical scavenging activity, *Moringa oleifera*, *Sauropus androgynus*

INTRODUCTION

Antioxidants play an important role in guarding the cells from oxidative damage due to free radicals¹. Free radicals are molecules that are easily formed during daily activities, such as exercising. Apart from natural formation, environmental exposure to free radicals, including UV light, smoke, and contaminated air, are common in daily life. The free radicals are highly unstable, which can induce oxidative stress that leads to cell damage and diseases. Antioxidants act as a reducing agent to reduce the reactive oxygen species which are in the form of free radicals². In contrast with synthetic antioxidants which have higher potential to impair health, a lot of studies have been carried out to

explore more natural oxidants from natural sources such as plants and animals³. Vegetables, fruits, and edible plants are the targets of researchers to study the antioxidant activity of the extracts of different plant parts such as roots, leaves, pods, seeds, fruits, and flowers. More and more researchers are putting efforts into exploring the ability of antioxidants obtained from natural sources in protecting consumers against diseases and aging^{4,5}.

Moringa oleifera (Lam.) is a tropical tree of Moringaceae family that natively grown in northern India⁶. Some common names of *Moringa oleifera* include moringa, the miracle tree, drumstick tree and horseradish tree. It is commonly known as kelor or

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murungai in Malaysia. *Moringa oleifera* is rich in nutrients, especially vitamins, and its leaves contain all essential amino acids⁷. Its leaves, root, bark, pods, seeds, flowers and fruits are consumed as dishes and drinks traditionally to treat influenza, diabetes, used as antiepileptic, diuretic, stimulant and anti-paralytic⁸. *Sauropus androgynus* (L.) Merr. is a tropical shrub of Phyllanthaceae family⁹. It is widely cultivated in East Malaysia, to be served as dishes. It is commonly known as katuk or cekur manis in East Malaysia. Other common names include sweet leaf and star gooseberry. The vitamin C, B1 and B2 compositions are high in *Sauropus androgynus* leaves. Traditionally, the leaves and roots were extracted and consumed to treat dysuria, hypertension, diarrhoea, and increase breast milk production. The leaf extracts have also been consumed to reduce body weight¹⁰.

AIM

There is a lack of data for the research on antioxidant activity assays for combination extract of *Moringa oleifera* and *Sauropus androgynus* leaves. Hence, this study aims to investigate the free radical scavenging potential of combination extract with that of the individual extracts by ABTS and DPPH free radical scavenging assays.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Chemicals

DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl), ABTS (2,2'-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) diammonium salt), potassium persulfate, ascorbic acid, BHT (butylated hydroxytoluene), 5% iron (III) chloride, sodium hydroxide, diluted hydrochloric acid, concentrated hydrochloric acid, concentrated sulphuric acid, chloroform, Dragendorff's reagent, Wagner's reagent, glacial acetic acid, 99% methanol.

2.2 Sample preparation and extraction.

The fresh leaves of *Moringa oleifera* and *Sauropus androgynus* were collected from local wet market in Sarawak, Malaysia. The leaves were cleaned using tap water and shade dried on a dry cloth in an air-circulated place until complete drying. The leaves were then crushed and stored in plastic containers separately in fridge until needed. The study was conducted among three samples, namely *Moringa oleifera* leaves, *Sauropus androgynus* leaves, and the combination extract of the two plant leaves (1:1 w/w). Maceration extraction was performed. 100g of each

plant sample combination was soaked in 99% methanol for two days with frequent mixing and stirring. The methanolic extracts obtained were filtered and concentrated to obtain dried extracts. The percentage yield was calculated, and the dry extracts were stored in the refrigerator (under 4°C).

2.3 Preliminary qualitative phytochemical screening

Extracts were screened for saponins, alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, phenols, steroids and terpenoids using appropriate methods with some modifications.^{11,12&13.}

2.4 Preparation of diluted sample extract and standard solutions

The solid extracts were dissolved in methanol using DMSO. The two standards, L-ascorbic acid and BHT solutions served as positive control were prepared by dissolving in distilled water. Five concentrations which included 1mg/mL, 0.5mg/mL, 0.25mg/mL, 0.125mg/mL and 0.0626mg/mL were prepared by serial dilution for each sample and standard. Seven micrograms concentrations which included 100µg/mL, 50µg/mL, 25µg/mL, 12.5µg/mL, 6.25µg/mL, 3.125µg/mL and 1.5625µg/mL were prepared for the two standards to obtain IC₅₀ value in free radical scavenging assays.

2.5 Determination of Free Radical Scavenging Potential (DPPH•)

A solution of 0.3mM DPPH• with violet colour was prepared by dissolving DPPH powder with methanol. 1mL of the solution was added to 2mL of each sample and standard concentrations, and to 2mL of methanol as negative control. The DPPH free radical solution decolorised upon addition of antioxidants. The absorbance was measured at 517nm using UV-vis spectrophotometer after 40 minutes. All the tests were done in triplicate and the percentage of inhibition for each sample and standard was calculated using the formula:

$$\frac{Abs_{control} - Abs_{sample}}{Abs_{control}} \times 100\%$$

2.6 Determination of Free Radical Scavenging Potential (ABTS•+)

About 7mM ABTS⁺ solution and 2.45mM potassium persulfate solution were prepared separately by dissolving the powders with distilled water. ABTS⁺ solution with blue green colour was prepared by reacting the two stock solutions in 1:1 ratio in dark for 14 hours at room temperature. The radical solution

was prepared only for two days use to ensure stability. Upon performing the assay, the radical solution was diluted with methanol to give an absorbance of 0.702 ± 0.002 at 734nm. Then, 3mL of the solution was added to 1mL of each sample and standard concentrations, and to 1mL of methanol as negative control. The ABTS free radical solution decolorised upon addition of antioxidants. The absorbance was measured at 734nm after 40 minutes. All the tests were performed in triplicate. The percentage of inhibition was calculated. Standard graph was formed from the data obtained, and the IC₅₀ value of each antioxidant was obtained from the graph.

RESULTS

Note: In all the following tables and figures, MO = *Moringa oleifera*; SA = *Sauropus androgynus*; MO+SA = combination extract

3.1 Pharmacognostical parameters

The study was carried out to qualitatively determine the phytochemical contents in the three leaf extract samples. The highest percentage of yield was observed in *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract (18.86%) (Table 1).

Table 1. Yield and Physical Characteristics of the Plant Extracts.

Plant samples	Weight (g)		% yield	Physical characteristics	Odour
	Plant sample	Dry extract yield			
MO	100	18.8648	18.86%	Sticky, oily	Characteristic odour
SA	100	12.8600	12.86%	Sticky, oily	Characteristic odour
MO+SA	100	13.9437	13.94%	Sticky, oily	Characteristic odour

As results of qualitative phytochemical screening tests, saponins, alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, and steroids were presented in both three samples.

Tannins were presented in *Moringa oleifera* and the combination extract, while absented in *Sauropus androgynus* leaf extract (Table 2).

Table 2. Phytochemical Screening of Plant Extracts

No.	Phytochemicals	Screening tests	MO	SA	MO+SA
1.	Tannins	Ferric chloride test	+	-	+
2.	Saponins	Froth test	+	+	+
3.	Alkaloids	Wagner's test	+	+	+
4.	Flavonoids	Sodium hydroxide test	+	+	+
5.	Glycosides	Keller-Killiani test	+	+	+
6.	Steroids	Salkowski test	+	+	+

Note: (+) indicates presence and (-) indicates absence

3.2 DPPH and ABTS assay

Table 3. Percentage Inhibition of DPPH Free Radical

Concentration (µg/mL)	MO	SA	MO+SA	AA	BHT
62.5	5.69 ± 0.05	1.36 ± 0.05	5.19 ± 0.05	96.45 ± 0.05	90.65 ± 1.07
25	16.31 ± 0.00	7.12 ± 0.05	14.42 ± 0.05	96.70 ± 0.05	95.42 ± 0.22
250	34.08 ± 0.05	18.25 ± 0.05	31.73 ± 0.05	96.84 ± 0.00	95.84 ± 0.38
500	68.17 ± 0.05	41.68 ± 0.08	65.89 ± 0.08	97.11 ± 0.10	95.28 ± 0.86
1000	95.17 ± 0.09	78.98 ± 0.05	96.01 ± 0.09	97.06 ± 0.19	95.75 ± 0.38

Figure 1. Graphical comparison of Percentage Inhibition of DPPH Free Radical

Table 4. Percentage Inhibition of ABTS Free Radical

Concentration (µg/mL)	MO	SA	MO+SA	AA	BHT
62.5	21.06 ± 0.00	20.84 ± 0.00	18.63 ± 0.00	99.78 ± 0.00	98.67 ± 0.00
125	39.47 ± 0.00	38.95 ± 0.13	34.37 ± 0.00	100.00 ± 0.00	99.78 ± 0.00
250	70.51 ± 0.00	67.18 ± 0.00	60.46 ± 0.13	100.00 ± 0.00	99.71 ± 0.13
500	99.56 ± 0.00	99.41 ± 0.13	98.67 ± 0.00	100.00 ± 0.00	99.85 ± 0.13
1000	99.78 ± 0.00	99.56 ± 0.00	99.78 ± 0.00	100.00 ± 0.00	100.00 ± 0.00

Figure 2. Percentage inhibition of ABTS free radical

Table 5. IC₅₀ value of five antioxidants for DPPH and ABTS assay

Assay	MO	SA	MO+SA	AA	BHT
DPPH	300.40 µg/mL	528.96 µg/mL	311.05 µg/mL	6.43 µg/mL	14.70 µg/mL
ABTS	149.77 µg/mL	154.24 µg/mL	171.18 µg/mL	2.94 µg/mL	7.70 µg/mL

Figure 3. IC₅₀ value in DPPH and ABTS scavenging

DISCUSSION

The study was carried out to compare the free radical scavenging activity between leaf extracts of *Moringa oleifera*, *Sauropus androgynus*, and the combination extract of the two plant leaves, with the standard antioxidants ascorbic acid and BHT. A higher percentage of free radical inhibition were detected in ascorbic acid and BHT than the three samples in both DPPH and ABTS assay (Table 3 - 4, Figure 1 - 2). The range was recorded from $1.36 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{g/mL}$ to $97.11 \pm 0.10 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for DPPH assay, and from $18.63 \pm 0.00 \mu\text{g/mL}$ to $100.00 \pm 0.00 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for ABTS assay at different concentrations. Among the five antioxidants, ascorbic acid possessed the lowest IC_{50} value in both DPPH ($6.43 \mu\text{g/mL}$) and ABTS ($2.94 \mu\text{g/mL}$) free radical scavenging assay (Table 5, Figure 3). Among the three samples, *Moringa oleifera* recorded the lowest IC_{50} value ($300.40 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for DPPH; $149.77 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for ABTS). *Sauropus androgynus* and the combination extract possessed the highest IC_{50} value in DPPH (SA: $528.96 \mu\text{g/mL}$) and ABTS (MO+SA: $171.18 \mu\text{g/mL}$) free radical scavenging assay respectively. Normality test was performed for the data obtained. The results revealed some data were not normally distributed (i.e. significance value < 0.05 in Shapiro-Wilk test). Hence, a non-parametric test namely Kruskal-Wallis H test¹⁴ was performed for the determination of statistically significant difference between the sample groups. The choice of test was made provided more than three independent groups to be assessed¹⁵. The actual data were replaced with ranks for the test. The percentage of free radical inhibition was compared between the five antioxidants at each concentration. In both analysis of DPPH and ABTS free radical scavenging assay, a significant difference in the results between the five antioxidants was observed ($P < 0.05$). Among the five antioxidants, ascorbic acid shown the highest mean rank value, which indicated the highest performance in free radical scavenging activity. On the other hand, comparison was made between the three samples in both DPPH and ABTS free radical scavenging assay. Two analyses shown a significant different free radical scavenging potential among the three antioxidants ($P < 0.05$). Among the three samples, *Moringa oleifera* shown the highest performance in both free radical scavenging activity. *Sauropus androgynus* shown the lowest performance in DPPH assay, while the combination extract shown the lowest

performance in ABTS assay. An exception was observed at $1000 \mu\text{g/mL}$ in the analysis, where the combination extract shown a superior performance in DPPH assay, and common highest performance in ABTS assay. Overall, in the aspect of free radical scavenging potential, *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract possessed the highest antioxidant potential among the three samples. The combination extract shown a comparable high (in ABTS assay) or superior (in DPPH assay) antioxidant potential as compared to *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract at a higher extract concentration ($1000 \mu\text{g/mL}$). In comparison with the combination extract, *Sauropus androgynus* leaf extract possessed lower DPPH radical scavenging potential, but higher ABTS radical scavenging potential. This could be due to the higher ability of *Sauropus androgynus* leaf extract to scavenge ABTS free radical than DPPH free radical. Nevertheless, the rich vitamin⁸, such as thiamin and riboflavin¹⁶, and lipid contents¹⁷ in *Sauropus androgynus* promised its nutritive value for dietary and herbal supplement. Hence, this could be its value to be added in the herbal formulation of *Moringa oleifera*. The combination formulation could possess a higher nutritive value than individual formulation. Safriani et. al., 2021¹⁸ reported significant amounts of total flavonoid content and total phenolic content possessed by both *Moringa oleifera* ($15.44 \pm 0.03 \text{mg QE/g}$; $5.27 \pm 0.09 \text{mcg GAE/mg}$) and *Sauropus androgynus* ($6.58 \pm 0.01 \text{mg QE/g}$; $2.10 \pm 0.12 \text{mcg GAE/mg}$). The phenolic compounds and flavonoids obtained from the *Moringa oleifera* and *Sauropus androgynus* extracts were found to be the main components to possess the antioxidant activity^{18,19}. The age of *Moringa oleifera* leaves and choice of extraction solvent shown impact on their DPPH' activity as reported by Nobossé and colleagues. The results of the study recorded the highest total phenolic and flavonoid contents with highest DPPH' scavenging potential in the highest maturity leaves (60-day-old) and ethanolic extracts ($53.3\% - 71.1\%$)¹⁹. On the other hand, the concentration of solvent used for extraction of *Sauropus androgynus* leaves was reported by Hikmawanti et al to affect the acquisition of phytochemicals and hence affected its scavenging activity of DPPH free radical. 50% ethanol solvent was reported to extract the highest total phenolic and flavonoid content, and possessed the greatest

antioxidant activity (IC₅₀: 88.33 ppm) as compared to extracts using 70% and 96% ethanol solvent²⁰.

CONCLUSION

This study reports the antioxidant potential of *Moringa oleifera*, *Sauropus androgynus* methanolic leaf extracts, and the combination extract of the two plant leaves by DPPH and ABTS free radical scavenging assay. The presence of phytochemicals including tannins, saponins, alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, and steroids are observed in most of the extracts. The addition of *Sauropus androgynus* leaf extract in *Moringa oleifera* leaf herbal formulation is promising and considerable with its own nutritive value and the high free radical scavenging potential of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extracts. Further research of combination extract in different aspects could be conducted to prove its value.

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